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Report on Engagement to Industry**

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes a set of actions put in place for enhancing the engagement with the industrial community and presents the methodology for a market analysis in the RIANA project. Targeting specifically small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), RIANA aims to develop and deliver integrated research infrastructure services tailored to Europe’s nanoscience and nanotechnology innovation ecosystem. The following actions have been taken:

- A section for SME access proposals has been implemented on the RIANA webpage.
- The Platform of Industrial Contact Officers (PICO) has been established and a dedicated section for the Innovation Service delivered by the PICOs has been published on the RIANA webpage.
- A workflow has been implemented to identify and monitor industrially relevant opportunities via a continuous screening of academic user proposals.
- A workflow has been implemented for the identification of unused potential for upscaling processes and increase of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL).

Together, these action items match the Research Infrastructure access to the actual needs of SMEs and foster the exploitation of unused innovation potential.

1. Introduction

Today, industrial access to RI does not exploit its full potential, and there is clear evidence that specific support to industrial clients for easy access to the RI as well as access standardization accompanied by monitoring of the experiments is essential. This is particularly the case in rapidly evolving fields such as nanoscience and nanotechnology, where the highly diversified industry-environment spans from mature activities (e.g. nanomedicine) to developing methodologies and paths, as in the case of quantum systems and/or new electronics beyond classical semiconductors and energy materials.

In the RIANA project, WP 4 develops the framework and methodology required to tailor access support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), with the aim of helping them advance their technologies, increase their Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), and scale up their production processes. In addition, it provides an Innovation Service to facilitate industry-oriented access to research infrastructures (RI) and laboratories/networks included in RIANA. As a key objective of WP 4, the cooperation between industry and the RIs should result in a better and easier use of the RI potential by industry with a significant impact beyond the project duration.

Part of the effort in WP 4 is devoted to identifying the right level of engagement and communication with industrial communities in general and specifically with SMEs and start-up companies. In fact, nanotechnology-oriented innovations are rapidly changing their technological target across a range of sectors as their timely development needs customized access to the most advanced tools and testing facilities – and they are often available in analytical RI through RIANA.

Nanoscience and nanotechnology are central drivers of next-generation industrial innovation. Knowing that the transition of scientific insights from RI to the industrial domain is a strategic action for innovation and economic growth, it is necessary to not only establish methodologies for overcoming technology barriers, but also to screen market sectors to identify which are more fertile to possible applications, and to train scientists in communication with industrial partners. The Innovation Service recently implemented in RIANA (run by the Platform of Industrial Contact Officers (PICOs), Task 4.1) responds to both needs by tailoring access models and methodologies for industry aiming to align and accelerate RIANA activities towards market-driven objectives.

2. Objectives and strategy

A key objective of the RIANA Innovation Service is to allow smaller players in the industrial ecosystem to benefit from world-class scientific facilities to boost competitiveness and innovation capacity.

Qualified access to advanced scientific infrastructures and specialized instrumentation is often difficult for SMEs and start-ups, as expert knowledge may not be available within their own organizations. While large companies may possess substantial internal R&D capabilities, this is not necessarily the case for SMEs and start-ups. For the latter, access to RIs is even more critical, as limited financial and technical resources often restrict their ability to independently develop research capabilities and intellectual property (IP) that are key to turn innovation into sustainable business operation.

Within the EU project NFFA,¹ key aspects in the maturing process of techniques offered at RI have been identified for their effective transfer from concepts to routine access by SMEs as illustrated in Fig. 1. RIANA activities are perfectly aligned with this concept and we recognize that access to RIs alone is not sufficient. Therefore, we offer additional support: at lower TRL by the RIANA Science Service in WP 2 (central segments in Fig. 1), and at higher TRL, this support is provided by the RIANA Innovation Service in WP 4 (right segments in Fig. 1), namely the knowledge transfer from academia to industry.

Figure 1: Maturing process of a cutting-edge technique, adapted from the NFFA-EUROPE deliverable D11.20: position paper on sustainable business models.² In RIANA, lower-TRL support is provided by the Science Service implemented in WP 2, and higher-TRL support is implemented as Innovation Service in WP 4, both offering customized service for highest impact.

In a strategic approach, RIANA mitigates the fragmentation of activities and resources, fostering truly interdisciplinary collaboration and integrating activities with cohesive R&D goals. Embracing all aspects of R&D in nanoscience and nanotechnology, we prioritize research areas, methodologies, and tools that address global challenges in line with the EU strategies,³ and support the transfer from academic developments into industrial applications.

¹ <https://nffa.eu/>

² http://nffa-europe.nffa.eu/media/249267/d1120_nffa-europe-position-paper-on-sustainable-business-models.pdf

³ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy_en

3. Actions implemented

Translating the objectives presented in section 2 into action, RIANA has implemented the following workflows and activities to engage with the industrial community:

a) *Single entry point for SME access proposals*

A dedicated section for SME access proposals has been included on the RIANA webpage (<https://riana-project.eu/sme-user-access/>). For efficient workflows of proposal submission, evaluation, RI access, and reporting, the access portal for SME proposals mirrors the portal for academic proposals. For further details, we refer to deliverables D4.2 and D4.3.

b) *Platform of Industrial Contact Officers (PICO)*

A specific section devoted to the innovation service delivered by RIANA and industrial applications has been implemented on the RIANA webpage (<https://riana-project.eu/industry/>). The PICO team (Task 4.1) plays a particular role therein and has been established to facilitate the direct communication between industry and RIANA. In analogy to the Smart Science Cluster offering Science Service for academic users through WP 2, the PICOs offer Innovation Service to industrial users through WP 4. Recognizing that face-to-face communication and customized service are crucial for SMEs, the PICO team presents itself online (<https://riana-project.eu/pico-the-platform-of-industrial-contact-officers/>), accommodates requests from SMEs, and proactively reaches out to SMEs that may not yet be aware of the RIANA offers. Specifically, the PICO team

- (i) maps industrial needs to RI capabilities and identifies suitable access pathways,
- (ii) develops workflows that are adapted to industrial contexts with a focus on scalability and reproducibility, and
- (iii) provides guidance and methodology for integrating RIs into SMEs' technology development roadmaps.

Targeted dissemination actions of RIANA reaching out to SMEs include the NanoInnovation 2025 Conference and Exhibition (Rome),⁴ Rendez-Vous Carnot 2025 (Lyon),⁵ and Tech&Fest2025 (Grenoble).⁶

c) *Screening of academic proposals for innovation potential*

A workflow has been implemented to identify and monitor industrially relevant opportunities via a continuous screening of accepted proposals that have been submitted through the RIANA call for academic user proposals (Task 4.4). This workflow is based on a strong coordination of WP 4 with WP 2 and WP 3. Emphasis has been put on compliance with confidentiality, as IP and trust are delicate topics of utmost importance for SMEs.

In this workflow, a first analysis is conducted based solely on basic information (sample class and general proposal characteristics) after explicit written user consent. This process is in line with Fig. 1: starting from the academic need, monitoring the evolution of a specific case may intercept relevant applications with industrial potential. This screening is performed by specialized RIANA staff with experience transferring academic research at large-scale

⁴ <https://www.nanoinnovation2025.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.rdv-carnot.com/>

⁶ <https://www.tech-fest.fr/>

infrastructures into industrial applications. At a later stage, this screening is furthered by a market analysis to be performed within WP 4 based on the proposal database of all user proposals, not exclusively proposals submitted through the SME proposal route, as we see great unused potentials for innovation in academic proposals.

d) *Mapping RI capabilities with domains of high industrial impact*

A workflow has been implemented for the identification of unused potential for upscaling processes (Task 4.2.2), which is directly related to the market analysis as well yet at higher TRL than workflow c). We have selected three main domains with potential industrial impact, namely *laser manufacturing*, *silicon photonics*, and *sensing applications*. Mapping of these domains with capabilities at RIANA research infrastructures will be performed in the first semester 2026, and a cross check with user proposals will become part of the database for the market analysis.

Status of SME proposals

As of Feb. 2026, one proposal has been submitted and one proposal has been in preparation for the RIANA SME access route requesting access to cleanrooms, nanofabrication, scanning electron microscopy, focused ion beam sample preparation, and soft matter characterization. It is in the nature of a public report that no details can be given on confidential details of the proposals.

Status of academic proposals with industrial potential

Following the workflow detailed in point c) above, the industrial potential of academic proposals is periodically checked within Task 4.4. As of October 2025:

- > 10 academic proposals were identified with relevant industrial opportunities.
- For 4 proposals, the applicants have granted permission for a full analysis.
- For 3 more proposals, we are await of the user response/approval for a full analysis.

The full analysis of the industrial potential of academic proposals will be performed in the first semester of 2026 for the first time and periodically repeated as permission to perform the analysis will be granted by the user groups. As described in Task 4.2.3, WP 4 will propose users to identify materials, technologies and processes suited towards pre-commercialization and future production, as well as the possible presence of toxic, pollutants or rare materials, with the aim to substitute them with bio-compatible materials for innovation that is sustainable both at the ecological and economical level.

4. Methodology for market analysis in RIANA

A comprehensive analysis of all potential industrial sectors addressed through user projects in RIANA is well beyond the scope of the present report, given the vast breadth of the nanoscience and nanotechnology topic and the inclusive approach of RIANA being open to any type of research.

Hence, the methodology adopted here has been to

- (1) identify areas and sectors of interest, both proposed by the users (point 3c) or linked to developing tasks with possible growing TRL (point 3d), and
- (2) analyze the potential market.

We are currently in the first phase. A database will be created and feedback from users and selected laboratories within RIANA will be requested, under the supervision of the PICOs (Task 4.1) and in close collaboration with the Smart Science Cluster (WP 2), as the Junior Scientist are in permanent contact with the involved user groups and experts in the user science.

Due to the currently low number of submitted proposals, there is no exploitable database for a serious market analysis at the moment of writing this report. However, we have performed a pre-study based on (i) the first indications obtained from user projects and (ii) experience and feedback from sister projects like NFFA⁷ and ReMade@ARI.⁸

We have identified specific services and techniques available in RIANA with a good match to growing markets related to nanoscience and nanotechnology: *semiconductor industry, healthcare applications, life sciences, and photonics*. Services in these domains represent the initial core of the infrastructure's industrial offer and tackle sectors with a high societal impact. The following tools accessible through RIANA are particularly relevant in these domains, which is exemplarily shown for the semiconductor domain:

- a) *Focused Ion Beam (FIB)* is essential for structuring optical nanomaterials and semiconductor devices, linked to innovation in sectors such as nanophotonics, optical materials and devices, and integrated sensing. The semiconductor industry requires high-density, integrated, and miniaturized devices for which FIB techniques are ideal, and the market for failure analysis of electronics by FIB is expected to grow.
- b) *Atomic layer deposition (ALD)* and *molecular beam epitaxy (MBE)* are critical for chips targeting “More than Moore” and sensors in various applications. Be it to deposit dielectric gates in MOSFETs or layers to collect charge carriers in solar cells, these specialized depositions drive markets and key technology for Europe’s sovereignty.
- c) *Transmission electron microscopes (TEMs)*, *Scanning Electron Microscopes (SEMs)*, and in general *high-throughput scanning probes* enable atom-scale material analysis. With the miniaturization of chips and the onset of quantum technologies, the high resolution and three-dimensional capacity of electron microscopy are vital in the semiconductor industry from R&D to process development, quality control, monitoring, and failure analysis.

⁷ <https://nffa.eu/>

⁸ <https://remade-project.eu/>

5. Conclusions and future activities

We have encountered a low response rate from SMEs regarding access to RIANA, which challenges a serious market analysis. The risk of a low SME response has been anticipated in the proposal phase already, and mitigation actions are being taken that are detailed in future deliverables of WP 4.

In contrast, the preliminary results of the screening of academic user proposals is very promising: our approach of analyzing the industrial potential of academic proposals has generally been well received, which is evidenced by the high number of user groups that have granted permission for a full analysis of the industrial potential. While the full analysis is yet to be done, we expect further academic proposals to be submitted and analyzed with respect to industrial exploitation in the course of the coming two years. We are confident that this analysis will identify numerous original scientific ideas with industrial potential that will be the core of deliverable D4.4 (Report on academic proposals of industrial interest) that is due in month 42.

As an ongoing activity, we continue market analysis activities throughout the RIANA project duration, building on the database including both SME proposals and academic proposals with possible industrial outcome. A survey will be prepared and distributed to RIANA infrastructures that host tools and offer techniques identified in the preliminary analysis of growing markets. Similarly, a survey will be sent to users who have already expressed their interest in industry-related activities.

Accordingly, near-future *action items* that will be tackled in close collaboration with WP 2 (Customised access to Science Service), WP 3 (Customised access to Research Infrastructures), and WP 6 (Outreach, dissemination, and impact) include:

- (I) Shape the Innovation Service to match the need of SMEs
- (II) Screen (a) the key technologies available across the infrastructures for industrial use and (b) evaluate the technologies with respect to potential TRL increase
- (III) Identify services for high-impact technological sectors
- (IV) Engage with industry via targeted dissemination actions raising awareness of RIANA
- (V) Conduct a survey to better understand industry needs and identify effective ways to engage with SMEs